

GRAPHNETS

CoSMoS Statistical Report - 2023

I. Oană, B.-E. Mihăilă-Pințoiu, M.-G. Hâncean

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1 Introduction

The 2023 Statistical Report of the CoSMoS project (<https://cosmos.unibuc.ro>) presents descriptive analyses based on an integrated dataset comprising information on the main topics of our project: (a) COVID-19 indicators, (b) human mobility data, and (c) weather characteristics. The integrated dataset was created by the authors of this report by combining COVID-19 indicators, human mobility data from Google, weather indicators from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), and social, demographic and economic data from Eurostat and UNDP. Where available, our dataset blends this information as daily, weekly, monthly and annual time-series for all the countries of the European Union, allowing for comparative analyses between countries or within countries.

• COVID-19 relevant data

To this day, the Our World in Data (OWID) website and repository remain one of the the best data sources for COVID-19 related data, given it's constant update and easy-access via their interactive platform or GitHub repository for bulk download. The team behind the OWID project maintains relevant COVID-19 pandemic statistics ([Our World in Data, 2023](#), [Mathieu et al. \(2023\)](#), [Hasell et al. \(2023\)](#)), by aggregating official records from national governments, international organizations, and academic projects dedicated to tracking or creating specific indicators (e.g., the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, the World Bank, or Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker, Blavatnik School of Government, University of Oxford). The data have a longitudinal nature with daily variations. While there are breaks in the time-series, given that national official statistics are no longer reported (or at least not in a format which can be integrated with data from other countries), the OWID team constantly updates their data, where publicly available information permits it. The complete OWID datasets are publicly available for download from their repository at: <https://github.com/owid/covid-19-data>. To these, we added weekly data from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) ([European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2023](#)).

• Mobility data from Google

Google Community Mobility Reports ([Google LLC, 2023](#)) were made available by Google to provide information about human mobility, which can help researchers in having a better understanding of mobility behaviors during the various stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. The mobility reports are comprised of longitudinal, daily data, about changes in human movement across six categories of places: (a) groceries and pharmacies; (b) retail and recreation; (c) parks; (d) transit stations; (e) workplaces; (f) residential places. Such changes are computed as the difference in movement and time spent from a baseline that was set as the median value of registered activity in the period Jan. 3rd – Feb. 6th 2020. The Google dataset is available at: <https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/> (the Global CSV file). The data is anonymized and aggregated, hence it doesn't allow for personal identification.

• Weather data

Data about weather indicators refers to: (a) air temperature at 2 meters surface, (b) air humidity at 2 meters surface, (c) precipitation, and (d) wind speed at 10 meters surface. These measures are presented separately for the summer and winter seasons. The summer season is comprised of June, July, and August. The winter season takes into consideration the months December, January, and February, with the exception of 2020 and 2023 for which the winter season takes into account only January and February. The weather data are monthly, from January 2020 to October 2023, and were accessed using the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store, using the *ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present* ([Hersbach et al., 2023](#)). We downloaded monthly data for the years 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023, summing to 46 months from January 2020 to October 2023. **The hour of reference for all the four weather indicators is 00:00.** The ERA5 dataset was downloaded from their platform, available at: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels-monthly-means?tab=form>

• Context data

Various social, demographic, and economic characteristics are important for understanding the way in which the COVID-19 pandemic can affect persons' health outcomes and behaviors (different dynamics of infections, vaccinations), and governments' responses though pharmaceutical or non-pharmaceutical interventions. In this report, we present country level data about: (a) population level ([Eurostat, 2023h](#)), (b) population

density (Eurostat, 2023g), (c) the median age of the general population (Eurostat, 2023i), (d) proportion of persons aged 65 or more (Eurostat, 2023i), (e) GDP per capita (Eurostat, 2023e), (f) changes in GDP per capita (Eurostat, 2023b), (g) overall healthcare expenditure as percentage of GDP (Eurostat, 2023c), (h) excessive mortality (Eurostat, 2023a), (i) hospital discharges for cardio-vascular diseases (Eurostat, 2023d), (j) proportion of persons at risk of poverty and social exclusion (Eurostat, 2023f), and (k) Human Development Index (United Nations Development Program, 2023). These data do not have the same longitudinal granularity as the COVID-19, mobility, and weather related measurements. Usually, they are yearly reported data. For all these indicators, we present national distributions and EU level descriptive statistics starting from 2019 to the last year for which data are available.

This report presents the main indicators for these topics, such as the number of COVID-19 infections, deaths tests, and vaccination rates; increases or decreases among a series mobility indicators; and the dynamic of weather characteristics. To these we also add contextual information based on series of social, demographic, and economic indicators. The aforementioned indicators are presented in this report at the national level and, for brevity, presented as averages for a certain year or season within a year. Even if the focus is on Romania, for comparative purposes we also present data from other countries or higher aggregation levels. Such comparisons are either with all other countries from the European Union, for which data are available, or with average values at the EU level. The end date used for data actualization is 17.11.2023.

A description of the dataset can be found at the end of this report, Table **METADATA**. The table gives information about: (a) variable name, (b) description, (c) format type and unit of measurement (where is the case), (d) temporal coverage - whether the data are daily, weekly, monthly time-series, or annual, (f) data source, (g) links for downloading data and further documentation about the indicators (in the online version of the file "Metadata.csv"). As a last point, we mention that the dataset created by the members of the CoSMoS project comes in two forms: CSV and RDS. The difference between the two is that the latter contains the data as a R **sf object** with a special **geometry** column, which permits users to create static or dynamic maps with EU countries, NUTS0 level. The data, along with other files (i.e., updated versions of this report and Metadata.csv), can be downloaded from: <https://zenodo.org/records/10171777>.

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The dataset is free to use, by attribution (CC-BY 4.0). If you use the dataset, please cite as: Oană, I., Mihăilă-Pințoiu, B.-E., & Hâncean, M.-G. (2023). COVID-19 integrated dataset: a unique blend of social dynamics and weather conditions (Version number). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10171777>

2 COVID-19 dynamics

2.0.1 Number of COVID-19 cases

Figure 1

Table 1: Evolution of total cases (per mil.), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	6290.23	8928.69	0.00	2449.29	33290.33	363	99.73
Romania	6803.18	9060.90	0.15	2488.04	31941.22	308	84.62
2021							
European Union	71908.73	19560.16	33472.04	71891.34	119091.41	365	100.00
Romania	58369.40	17039.70	32161.06	54977.78	91927.27	365	100.00
2022							
European Union	313598.90	71107.63	119660.96	325936.18	397672.21	365	100.00
Romania	149307.72	19524.04	92012.11	148503.02	168291.09	365	100.00
2023							
European Union	406397.65	2951.31	398574.53	407799.86	409718.88	313	98.43
Romania	172772.36	2527.09	168291.09	173211.21	178013.07	313	100.00

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

2.0.2 Number of deaths

Figure 3

Table 3: Evolution of total deaths (per mil.), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	263.12	206.89	0.01	276.89	859.54	362	99.45
Romania	220.75	212.82	0.10	139.70	793.32	284	78.02
2021							
European Union	1574.44	273.35	863.82	1662.76	2033.13	365	100.00
Romania	1704.25	614.58	802.01	1722.39	2986.58	365	100.00
2022							
European Union	2447.20	161.63	2035.26	2468.57	2668.53	365	100.00
Romania	3318.54	120.06	2988.51	3343.92	3427.09	365	100.00
2023							
European Union	2743.07	25.99	2674.41	2756.00	2770.13	313	97.20
Romania	3462.32	15.72	3427.09	3468.74	3487.82	313	100.00

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

Figure 4

Table 4: Evolution of new deaths (per mil.; 7-day rolling average), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	2.34	2.98	0.00	0.72	9.07	359	98.63
Romania	2.16	2.51	0.00	1.17	8.49	359	98.63
2021							
European Union	3.24	2.30	0.22	3.33	7.86	365	100.00
Romania	6.04	5.43	0.08	4.27	23.08	365	100.00
2022							
European Union	1.76	1.20	0.63	1.28	4.76	365	100.00
Romania	1.22	1.69	0.00	0.48	7.06	365	100.00
2023							
European Union	0.33	0.31	0.02	0.22	1.40	313	97.20
Romania	0.19	0.12	0.02	0.21	0.60	309	98.72

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

2.0.3 Number of tests

Figure 5

Table 5: Evolution of total tests (per 1,000), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	176.45	177.28	0.00	112.60	632.09	326	100
Romania	84.17	75.49	0.14	63.34	231.75	42	100
2021							
European Union	2360.43	1065.86	624.25	2326.32	4541.81	365	100
Romania	518.87	185.02	236.29	491.29	863.80	52	100
2022							
European Union	5063.80	540.83	4222.58	4932.16	8320.24	174	100
Romania	995.54	74.06	884.30	1004.27	1099.95	10	100

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

Figure 6

Table 6: Evolution of new tests (per 1,000; 7-day moving average), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	1.78	1.40	0.00	1.43	5.34	327	100
Romania	0.82	0.44	0.00	0.92	1.57	281	100
2021							
European Union	8.75	1.94	3.56	8.35	14.01	365	100
Romania	1.73	0.61	0.62	1.54	3.28	365	100
2022							
European Union	8.87	5.79	1.61	9.74	17.58	174	100
Romania	3.30	0.70	2.08	3.19	4.54	69	100

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

Figure 7

Table 7: Evolution of positive rate (% of total tests), EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	6.00	4.87	0.00	3.63	14.86	312	100
Romania	11.45	9.88	1.70	6.53	76.75	273	100
2021							
European Union	6.78	3.43	1.16	7.00	16.34	365	100
Romania	8.46	7.48	0.18	7.84	30.42	365	100
2022							
European Union	21.82	5.14	12.92	21.61	31.71	174	100
Romania	20.60	10.62	2.81	21.28	36.13	69	100

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

2.0.4 COVID-19 Vaccination

Fully vaccinated persons in the EU

Country level data for fully vaccinated persons, update Nov. 2023

Data: Our World in Data

Figure 8

Table 8: Vaccination levels in the EU [2021-2023] - descriptives for fully vaccinated persons

	people_fully_vaccinated_per_hundred 2021	people_fully_vaccinated_per_hundred 2022	people_fully_vaccinated_per_hundred 2023
Mean	63.34	68.99	72.20
Std.Dev	17.40	14.27	12.70
Min	5.85	30.59	30.64
Q1	56.09	62.28	67.08
Median	67.84	72.03	74.19
Q3	75.77	78.66	80.19
Max	83.13	88.38	88.42
MAD	11.76	11.30	9.41
IQR	16.69	15.67	12.40
CV	0.27	0.21	0.18
Skewness	-1.58	-0.94	-1.51
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.46	0.49
Kurtosis	2.42	0.27	2.74
N.Valid	27.00	26.00	22.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	96.30	81.48

Note:

Data source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

2.0.5 Governmental responses, the Stringency Index

Stringency index

Temporal dynamics, EU means and Romania

Data source: OWID COVID-19 dataset from Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker, Blavatnik School of Government

Table 9: Stringency index evolution, EU and RO - descriptive statistics

Location	Mean	Sd	Min	Med	Max	N.valid	Pct.valid
2020							
European Union	48.89	23.67	0.00	48.34	81.89	364	100
Romania	52.10	26.16	0.00	49.07	87.04	364	100
2021							
European Union	53.20	12.04	39.44	45.53	70.73	365	100
Romania	62.25	11.37	42.58	67.59	76.85	365	100
2022							
European Union	19.65	10.45	11.41	14.75	45.41	365	100
Romania	18.89	16.47	11.11	11.11	56.48	365	100

Note:

Source: OWID COVID-19 dataset

3 Social, demographic, and economic indicators

3.0.1 Population

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Population levels in the EU

Country level data, Jan. 2023

Data: Eurostat tps00001

Figure 13

Table 10: Population levels in the EU [2019-2023] - descriptives

	population.2019	population.2020	population.2021	population.2022	population.2023
Mean	16539232.56	16573527.07	16555575.85	16545751.52	16606958.22
Std.Dev	22256817.72	22293137.42	22276351.79	22287356.66	22416690.30
Min	493559.00	514564.00	516100.00	520971.00	542051.00
Q1	2794184.00	2794090.00	2795680.00	2805998.00	2857279.00
Median	8858775.00	8901064.00	8932664.00	8978929.00	9104772.00
Q3	17282163.00	17407585.00	17475415.00	17590672.00	17811291.00
Max	83019213.00	83166711.00	83155031.00	83237124.00	84358845.00
MAD	8991362.62	9054199.65	9098692.48	9151987.50	9262533.12
IQR	10933626.00	11038885.00	11099073.50	11269996.00	11428561.00
CV	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35
Skewness	1.71	1.71	1.71	1.72	1.73
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	1.71	1.71	1.72	1.74	1.82
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, tps00001

3.0.2 Density

Figure 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Density levels in the EU
Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat demo_r_d3dens

Figure 17

Table 11: Density levels in the EU [2019-2022] - descriptives

	density.2019	density.2020	density.2021	density.2022
Mean	182.13	182.66	184.40	184.92
Std.Dev	302.34	305.09	311.74	313.79
Min	18.20	18.10	18.20	18.20
Q1	71.90	71.90	72.40	70.70
Median	106.10	106.30	106.60	106.40
Q3	138.50	138.50	138.90	139.50
Max	1595.10	1610.40	1646.40	1656.70
MAD	49.37	49.67	50.41	49.07
IQR	66.00	66.00	66.25	65.80
CV	1.66	1.67	1.69	1.70
Skewness	3.80	3.81	3.84	3.84
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	14.74	14.83	14.98	14.99
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, demo_r_d3dens

3.0.3 Median age

Figure 18

Figure 19

Figure 20

Median age in the EU

Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat, demo_pjanind

Figure 21

Table 12: Median age in the EU [2019-2022] - descriptives

	median.age.p_2019	median.age.p_2020	median.age.p_2021	median.age.p_2022
Mean	42.54	42.72	42.94	43.23
Std.Dev	2.25	2.29	2.29	2.37
Min	37.70	37.70	38.00	38.30
Q1	41.00	41.30	41.60	41.90
Median	42.70	43.00	43.30	43.50
Q3	44.00	44.20	44.40	45.10
Max	46.80	47.20	47.60	48.00
MAD	1.93	1.78	2.08	2.37
IQR	2.65	2.65	2.70	2.95
CV	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Skewness	-0.39	-0.38	-0.31	-0.20
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	-0.34	-0.38	-0.42	-0.55
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, demo_pjanind

3.0.4 Persons aged 65 or older

Figure 22

Figure 23

Figure 24

Population over 65 in the EU
Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat, demo_pjanind

Figure 25

Table 13: Population 'over 65' in the EU [2019-2022] - descriptives

	age.over65_2019	age.over65_2020	age.over65_2021	age.over65_2022
Mean	19.33	19.61	19.91	20.19
Std.Dev	2.17	2.19	2.19	2.28
Min	14.10	14.40	14.60	14.80
Q1	18.70	18.90	19.20	19.40
Median	19.60	19.90	20.10	20.30
Q3	20.60	21.00	21.40	21.70
Max	22.90	23.20	23.50	23.80
MAD	1.33	1.48	1.33	1.33
IQR	1.70	1.80	1.85	1.95
CV	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
Skewness	-0.80	-0.79	-0.81	-0.68
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	0.19	0.22	0.30	0.17
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, nama_10_pc

3.0.5 Real GDP / capita

Figure 26

Figure 27

Figure 28

(Real) GDP/capita in the EU
Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat, nama_10_pc

Figure 29

Table 14: GDP levels in the EU (real) in the EU [2019-2022] - descriptives

	gdp.real_2019	gdp.real_2020	gdp.real_2021	gdp.real_2022
Mean	27754.81	26625.56	28487.78	29370.37
Std.Dev	17554.49	17491.47	18792.10	19147.76
Min	6630.00	6400.00	6950.00	7680.00
Q1	14060.00	14060.00	14870.00	15100.00
Median	23170.00	20840.00	23270.00	24320.00
Q3	37150.00	35390.00	36740.00	37780.00
Max	84280.00	82130.00	86690.00	86130.00
MAD	14974.26	13195.14	14203.31	14381.22
IQR	21875.00	20310.00	20950.00	21735.00
CV	0.63	0.66	0.66	0.65
Skewness	1.34	1.41	1.45	1.43
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	1.77	1.79	1.79	1.63
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, nama_10_pc

3.0.6 GDP change

Figure 30

Figure 31

GDP change in the EU
Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat, nama_10_gdp

Figure 32

Table 15: GDP change in the EU [2020-2022] - descriptives

	GDP.change_2020	GDP.change_2021	GDP.change_2022
Mean	-4.37	7.20	3.89
Std.Dev	3.62	2.86	2.12
Min	-11.20	3.20	-0.50
Q1	-7.50	5.70	2.40
Median	-3.90	6.80	3.70
Q3	-2.40	8.20	5.30
Max	6.60	15.10	9.40
MAD	2.52	1.63	1.93
IQR	4.65	2.05	2.75
CV	-0.83	0.40	0.55
Skewness	0.59	1.13	0.41
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	1.15	1.08	-0.01
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, nama_10_gdp

3.0.7 Healthcare expenditure

Figure 33

Figure 34

Healthcare expenditure in the EU
Country level data, 2021

Data: Eurostat, hlth_sha11_hf

Figure 35

Table 16: Healthcare expenditure in the EU - % GDP [2019-2021] - descriptives

	GDP.change_2020	GDP.change_2021	GDP.change_2022
Mean	-4.37	7.20	3.89
Std.Dev	3.62	2.86	2.12
Min	-11.20	3.20	-0.50
Q1	-7.50	5.70	2.40
Median	-3.90	6.80	3.70
Q3	-2.40	8.20	5.30
Max	6.60	15.10	9.40
MAD	2.52	1.63	1.93
IQR	4.65	2.05	2.75
CV	-0.83	0.40	0.55
Skewness	0.59	1.13	0.41
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	1.15	1.08	-0.01
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, hlth_sha11_hf

3.0.8 Excess mortality

Figure 36

Figure 37

Excessive mortality in the EU

Country level data, 2023

Data: Eurostat, hlth_sha11_hf

Figure 38

Table 17: Excess mortality in the EU - [2021-2023] - descriptives

	exc.mortality_2021	exc.mortality_2022	exc.mortality_2023
Mean	16.07	11.10	2.80
Std.Dev	9.58	4.58	5.98
Min	0.90	3.80	-7.90
Q1	9.10	7.40	-0.90
Median	14.20	11.20	3.90
Q3	21.70	13.60	7.10
Max	38.00	23.90	13.70
MAD	9.19	4.45	6.23
IQR	11.85	5.30	7.30
CV	0.60	0.41	2.14
Skewness	0.56	0.58	-0.09
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	-0.54	0.33	-0.99
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, demo_mexrt

3.0.9 Hospital discharges due to CVDs

Figure 39

Figure 40

Hospital discharges for CVDs in the EU

Country level data, 2021

Data: Eurostat, hlth_co_disch2

Figure 41

Table 18: Hospital discharges for CVDs in the EU - [2019-2021] - descriptives

	hosp.disch.cvd_2019	hosp.disch.cvd_2020	hosp.disch.cvd_2021
Mean	2336.27	1883.81	1933.85
Std.Dev	1011.71	777.31	660.31
Min	929.90	474.20	1060.70
Q1	1367.30	1279.05	1511.30
Median	2038.80	1732.85	1822.10
Q3	3051.10	2262.30	2112.70
Max	4697.40	3618.00	3343.70
MAD	1090.45	771.25	445.82
IQR	1455.90	902.28	581.95
CV	0.43	0.41	0.34
Skewness	0.59	0.43	0.64
SE.Skewness	0.48	0.47	0.49
Kurtosis	-0.56	-0.56	-0.59
N.Valid	23.00	24.00	22.00
Pct.Valid	95.83	100.00	91.67

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, hlth_co_disch2

3.0.10 Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion

Figure 42

Figure 43

Figure 44

Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion in the EU
Country level data, 2022

Data: Eurostat, ilc_peps01n

Figure 45

Table 19: Persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion in the EU - [2019-2022] - descriptives

	pov.se.risk_2019	pov.se.risk_2020	pov.se.risk_2021	pov.se.risk_2022
Mean	20.91	20.63	20.69	20.69
Std.Dev	5.72	5.63	5.53	5.28
Min	12.10	11.50	10.70	11.80
Q1	17.30	16.80	17.20	16.70
Median	20.00	19.90	20.00	19.90
Q3	24.60	24.50	23.50	24.60
Max	36.10	35.60	34.50	34.40
MAD	5.19	4.60	4.15	5.04
IQR	6.85	6.75	5.70	7.60
CV	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.26
Skewness	0.89	0.92	0.64	0.80
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	0.31	0.52	-0.02	0.23
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, ilc_peps01n

3.0.11 Human Development Index

Figure 46

Figure 47

Human Development Index scores in the EU
Country level data, 2021

Data: UNDP; Trends in Human Development Index, 1990–2021

Figure 48

Table 20: Human Development Index in the EU - [2019-2021] - descriptives

	HDI_2019	HDI_2020	HDI_2021
Mean	0.90	0.90	0.90
Std.Dev	0.04	0.04	0.04
Min	0.81	0.80	0.80
Q1	0.87	0.87	0.87
Median	0.90	0.89	0.90
Q3	0.94	0.93	0.94
Max	0.95	0.95	0.95
MAD	0.04	0.04	0.05
IQR	0.06	0.05	0.06
CV	0.04	0.04	0.05
Skewness	-0.51	-0.50	-0.57
SE.Skewness	0.45	0.45	0.45
Kurtosis	-0.54	-0.43	-0.46
N.Valid	27.00	27.00	27.00
Pct.Valid	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Eurostat, ilc_peps01n

4 Google Mobility Reports

Figure 49

Figure 50

Figure 51

Figure 52

Figure 53

Figure 54

Table 21: Google Mobility in the EU - descriptives

	grocery.pharmacy_gm	parks_gm	residential_gm	retail.recreation_gm	transit.stations_gm	workplaces_gm
2020						
Mean_2020	-2.97	35.96	7.10	-19.22	-22.65	-23.81
Std.Dev_2020	21.17	62.88	8.29	27.66	23.42	19.71
Min_2020	-95.25	-89.79	-14.77	-96.03	-91.57	-92.00
Median_2020	-0.18	20.31	5.59	-12.98	-21.48	-23.00
Max_2020	198.32	391.00	48.03	71.88	125.25	70.00
N.Valid_2020	8344.00	8272.00	8344.00	8346.00	8346.00	8343.00
Pct.Valid_2020	99.98	99.11	99.98	100.00	100.00	99.96
2021						
Mean_2021	15.30	50.33	4.24	-8.57	-10.68	-18.67
Std.Dev_2021	25.60	67.45	6.14	27.02	28.19	16.06
Min_2021	-95.00	-74.26	-14.68	-93.31	-80.02	-89.21
Median_2021	15.00	33.72	3.71	-4.95	-13.60	-17.12
Max_2021	246.19	526.75	39.62	97.62	221.75	81.50
N.Valid_2021	9490.00	9490.00	9490.00	9490.00	9490.00	9490.00
Pct.Valid_2021	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2022						
Mean_2022	24.93	70.43	2.29	4.77	8.19	-10.26
Std.Dev_2022	25.24	68.67	4.26	19.63	35.13	15.74
Min_2022	-91.47	-48.00	-12.28	-82.00	-59.27	-86.00
Median_2022	21.93	56.72	2.05	3.00	2.39	-9.03
Max_2022	271.71	567.00	25.58	113.11	285.12	82.90
N.Valid_2022	7488.00	7488.00	7488.00	7488.00	7488.00	7488.00
Pct.Valid_2022	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Google Community Mobility Reports

5 Weather indicators

5.0.1 Air temperature (2m)

Air temperature (2m) in the winter – 2023

Country level data (Average of mean temperatures in January, February)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 55

Air temperature (2m) in the summer – 2023

Country level data (Average of mean temperatures in June, July, August)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 56

5.0.2 Air humidity (2m)

Air humidity (2m) in the winter – 2023

Country level data (Mean of air humidity scores in January, February)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 57

Air humidity (2m) in the summer – 2023

Country level data (Mean of air humidity scores in June, July, August)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 58

5.0.3 Total precipitation per hour

Precipitation in the winter – 2023

Country level data (Mean of precipitation scores in January, February)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 59

Precipitation in the summer – 2023

Country level data (Mean of precipitation scores in June, July, August)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 60

5.0.4 Wind speed (10m)

Wind speed (10 m) in the winter – 2023

Country level data (Mean of wind speed scores in January, February)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 61

Wind speed (10 m) in the summer – 2023

Country level data (Mean of wind speed scores in June, July, August)

Data: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Figure 62

Table 22: Weather in the EU - descriptive statistics for Summer values

	temperature.2m - Summer	total.precipitation - Summer	temperature.dewpoint.2m - Summer	windspeed.10m - Summer
2020				
Mean_2020	19.12	2.72	12.92	2.84
Std.Dev_2020	2.92	1.30	1.94	0.67
Min_2020	14.25	0.03	8.54	1.83
Median_2020	18.56	2.78	12.62	2.86
Max_2020	26.49	5.69	17.77	4.49
N.Valid_2020	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2020	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2021				
Mean_2021	19.56	2.64	13.28	2.78
Std.Dev_2021	3.02	1.20	1.68	0.61
Min_2021	14.81	0.05	9.00	1.78
Median_2021	18.94	2.80	13.50	2.79
Max_2021	27.39	5.19	17.53	4.46
N.Valid_2021	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2021	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2022				
Mean_2022	20.15	2.19	12.91	2.79
Std.Dev_2022	3.11	0.97	1.76	0.56
Min_2022	14.45	0.07	9.21	1.91
Median_2022	19.44	2.10	12.95	2.74
Max_2022	26.75	4.98	17.82	4.35
N.Valid_2022	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2022	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2023				
Mean_2023	20.15	2.19	12.91	2.79
Std.Dev_2023	3.11	0.97	1.76	0.56
Min_2023	14.45	0.07	9.21	1.91
Median_2023	19.44	2.10	12.95	2.74
Max_2023	26.75	4.98	17.82	4.35
N.Valid_2023	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2023	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

Table 23: Weather in the EU - descriptive statistics for Winter values

	temperature.2m - Winter	total.precipitation - Winter	temperature.dewpoint.2m - Winter	windspeed.10m - Winter
2020				
Mean_2020	4.05	2.48	1.23	3.81
Std.Dev_2020	3.55	0.82	3.10	1.25
Min_2020	-3.61	1.41	-5.05	2.06
Median_2020	3.91	2.48	0.67	3.76
Max_2020	12.57	4.61	7.72	6.36
N.Valid_2020	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2020	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2021				
Mean_2021	1.84	2.57	-0.79	3.38
Std.Dev_2021	5.41	0.87	4.75	0.80
Min_2021	-10.18	1.41	-11.72	2.03
Median_2021	2.14	2.54	-0.48	3.27
Max_2021	13.34	4.44	7.84	5.14
N.Valid_2021	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2021	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2022				
Mean_2022	3.00	2.27	0.00	3.67
Std.Dev_2022	4.46	0.50	3.80	1.10
Min_2022	-7.06	1.24	-8.55	2.02
Median_2022	3.12	2.30	0.06	3.58
Max_2022	12.77	2.90	7.72	6.22
N.Valid_2022	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2022	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2023				
Mean_2023	3.00	2.27	0.00	3.67
Std.Dev_2023	4.46	0.50	3.80	1.10
Min_2023	-7.06	1.24	-8.55	2.02
Median_2023	3.12	2.30	0.06	3.58
Max_2023	12.77	2.90	7.72	6.22
N.Valid_2023	26.00	26.00	26.00	26.00
Pct.Valid_2023	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Note:

Data source: Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)

6 Metadata

Table 24: Metadata

Variable name	Description	Unit / Format	Coverage	Source
COUNTRY	Country name	character	-	-
CNTR_CODE	Country code, alpha-2 by Eurostat style guide	character	-	Eurostat
CNTR_ISO3	Country code by ISO 3166 international standard	character	Daily	-
Date	Date	Date: YYYY-MM-DD	-	-
YearWeekISO	Year and Week	YYYY-Www (e.g., 2020-W01)	-	-
Year	Year	character	-	-
Month	Month of year	character from '01' to '12'	-	-
Week	Week number	character, format 'W0n' (e.g., W01, W02)	-	-
Season	Season	character	-	-
cntr_year_week_id	Column containing an ID code combining CNTR_ISO3 and YearWeekISO	character	-	-
total_cases	Total number of COVID-19 confirmed cases	Number of COVID-19 cases	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
total_cases_per_million	Total number of COVID-19 confirmed cases per 1 million people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 cases / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_cases	Number of new confirmed COVID-19 cases	Number of COVID-19 cases	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_cases_per_million	Number of new confirmed COVID-19 cases per 1 million people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 cases / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_cases_smoothed_per_million	Number of new confirmed COVID-19 cases per 1 million people in the general population, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of COVID-19 cases / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
total_deaths	Total number of deaths of COVID-19	Number of COVID-19 deaths	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
total_deaths_per_million	Total number of deaths of COVID-19 per 1 million people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 deaths / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_deaths	Number of new deaths of COVID-19	Number of COVID-19 deaths	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_deaths_smoothed	Number of new deaths of COVID-19, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of COVID-19 deaths	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_deaths_per_million	Number of new deaths of COVID-19 per 1 million people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 deaths / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
new_deaths_smoothed_per_million	Number of new deaths of COVID-19 per 1 million people in the general population, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of COVID-19 deaths / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from COVID-19 Dashboard by the WHO
total_tests	Total number of tests for COVID-19	Number of COVID-19 tests	Daily	OWID from national government reports
total_tests_per_thousand	Total number of tests for COVID-19 per 1,000 people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 tests / 1,000	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_tests	Number of new tests for COVID-19, computed for consecutive days	Number of COVID-19 tests	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_tests_smoothed	Number of new tests for COVID-19, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of COVID-19 tests	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_tests_per_thousand	Number of new tests for COVID-19 per 1,000 people in the general population	Number of COVID-19 tests / 1,000	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_tests_smoothed_per_thousand	Number of new tests for COVID-19 per 1,000 people in the general population, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of COVID-19 tests / 1,000	Daily	OWID from national government reports
positive_rate	The share of COVID-19 tests that are positive, computed using a 7-day rolling average	% positive COVID-19 tests	Daily	OWID from national government reports
total_vaccinations	Total number of vaccination doses administered	Number of doses	Daily	OWID from national government reports
people_vaccinated	Total number of persons who received at least one vaccine dose	Number of persons	Daily	OWID from national government reports
people_fully_vaccinated	Total number of persons fully vaccinated (according to the vaccination protocol for each type of vaccine)	Number of persons	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_vaccinations	Number of new administered vaccination doses	Number of doses	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_vaccinations_smoothed	Number of new administered vaccination doses, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of doses	Daily	OWID from national government reports
total_vaccinations_per_hundred	Total number of vaccination doses administered by 100 people in the general population	Number of doses / 100	Daily	OWID from national government reports
people_vaccinated_per_hundred	Number of persons vaccinated with at least one dose per 100 people in the general population	Number of persons / 100	Daily	OWID from national government reports
people_fully_vaccinated_per_hundred	Number of persons fully vaccinated per 100 people in the general population (according to the vaccination protocol for each type of vaccine)	Number of persons / 100	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_vaccinations_smoothed_per_million	Number of new administered vaccination doses per 1 million people in the general population, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of doses / 1,000,000	Daily	OWID from national government reports
new_people_vaccinated_smoothed	Number of persons receiving their first vaccination dose, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of persons	Daily	OWID from national government reports

Table 24: Metadata (continued)

Variable name	Description	Unit / Format	Coverage	Source
new_people_vaccinated_smoothed_per_hund	Number of persons receiving their first vaccination dose per 100 people in the general population, computed using a 7-day rolling average	Number of persons / 100	Daily	OWID from national government reports
total_boosters	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a booster (according to the vaccination protocol for each type of vaccine)	Number of doses	Daily	OWID from national government reports
total_boosters_per_hundred	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a booster per 100 people in the general population (according to the vaccination protocol for each type of vaccine)	Number of doses / 100	Daily	OWID from national government reports
FirstDose_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as first dose in a given week	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
SecondDose_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as second dose in a given week	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
DoseAdditional1_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a first booster shot in a given week (after a complete standard primary course)	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
DoseAdditional2_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a second booster shot in a given week (after a complete standard primary course)	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
DoseAdditional3_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a third booster shot in a given week (after a complete standard primary course)	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
DoseAdditional4_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a fourth booster shot in a given week (after a complete standard primary course)	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
DoseAdditional5_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered as a fifth booster shot in a given week (after a complete standard primary course)	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
UnknownDose_ecdc	Total number of vaccination doses administered in a given week unknown if they are the first or second dose	Number of doses	Weekly	ECDC
stringency_index	Index measuring national governments' NPIs for combating COVID-19 spread (100 = strictest response)	Numeric	Daily	OWID from Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker, Blavatnik School of Government
population_2019	General population size in 2019 - country level	Number of persons	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: tps00001; year 2019
population_2020	General population size in 2020 - country level	Number of persons	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: tps00001; year 2020
population_2021	General population size in 2021 - country level	Number of persons	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: tps00001; year 2021
population_2022	General population size in 2022 - country level	Number of persons	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: tps00001; year 2022
population_2023	General population size in 2023 - country level	Number of persons	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: tps00001; year 2023
density_2019	Density size in 2019 - country level	Persons per square kilometer	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_r_d3dens; year 2019; NUTS0
density_2020	Density size in 2020 - country level	Persons per square kilometer	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_r_d3dens; year 2020; NUTS0
density_2021	Density size in 2021 - country level	Persons per square kilometer	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_r_d3dens; year 2021; NUTS0
density_2022	Density size in 2022 - country level	Persons per square kilometer	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_r_d3dens; year 2021; NUTS0
median.age.f_2019	Median age of women in 2019 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2019; indicator FMEDAGEPOP
median.age.f_2020	Median age of women in 2020 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2020; indicator FMEDAGEPOP
median.age.f_2021	Median age of women in 2021 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2021; indicator FMEDAGEPOP
median.age.f_2022	Median age of women in 2022 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2022; indicator FMEDAGEPOP
median.age.m_2019	Median age of men in 2019 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2019; indicator MMEDAGEPOP
median.age.m_2020	Median age of men in 2020 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2020; indicator MMEDAGEPOP
median.age.m_2021	Median age of men in 2021 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2021; indicator MMEDAGEPOP
median.age.m_2022	Median age of men in 2022 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2022; indicator MMEDAGEPOP

Table 24: Metadata (continued)

Variable name	Description	Unit / Format	Coverage	Source
median.age.p_2019	Median age of the general population in 2019 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2019; indicator MEDAGEPOP
median.age.p_2020	Median age of the general population in 2020 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2020; indicator MEDAGEPOP
median.age.p_2021	Median age of the general population in 2021 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2021; indicator MEDAGEPOP
median.age.p_2022	Median age of the general population in 2021 - country level	Median age	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2022; indicator MEDAGEPOP
age.over65_2019	Share of population aged 65 or more in 2019 - country level	% Persons 65+	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2019; indicator PC_Y65_MAX
age.over65_2020	Share of population aged 65 or more in 2020 - country level	% Persons 65+	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2020; indicator PC_Y65_MAX
age.over65_2021	Share of population aged 65 or more in 2021 - country level	% Persons 65+	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2021; indicator PC_Y65_MAX
age.over65_2022	Share of population aged 65 or more in 2022 - country level	% Persons 65+	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_pjanind; year 2022; indicator PC_Y65_MAX
gdp.real_2019	GDP at market prices per capita in 2019, by 2010 chain-linked level series	Euro / capita in 2019 by 2010 chain-linked level series	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_pc; year 2019; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV10_EUR_HAB
gdp.real_2020	GDP at market prices per capita in 2020, by 2010 chain-linked level series	Euro / capita in 2020 by 2010 chain-linked level series	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_pc; year 2020; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV10_EUR_HAB
gdp.real_2021	GDP at market prices per capita in 2021, by 2010 chain-linked level series	Euro / capita in 2021 by 2010 chain-linked level series	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_pc; year 2021; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV10_EUR_HAB
gdp.real_2022	GDP at market prices per capita in 2022, by 2010 chain-linked level series	Euro / capita in 2022 by 2010 chain-linked level series	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_pc; year 2022; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV10_EUR_HAB
GDP.change_2020	GDP percentage change relative to previous period	% change from previous period	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_gdp; year 2019; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV_PCH_PRE
GDP.change_2021	GDP percentage change relative to previous period	% change from previous period	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_gdp; year 2021; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV_PCH_PRE
GDP.change_2022	GDP percentage change relative to previous period	% change from previous period	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: nama_10_gdp; year 2022; indicator B1GQ; unit CLV_PCH_PRE
hcexp_2019	Total healthcare expenditure as percentate of GDP in 2019	% of GDP	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_sha11_hf; year 2019; indicator TOT_HF; unit PC_GDP
hcexp_2020	Total healthcare expenditure as percentate of GDP in 2020	% of GDP	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_sha11_hf; year 2020; indicator TOT_HF; unit PC_GDP
hcexp_2021	Total healthcare expenditure as percentate of GDP in 2021	% of GDP	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_sha11_hf; year 2021; indicator TOT_HF; unit PC_GDP
exc.mortality_month	Monthly excess mortality from 2021-2023 as percentage change from expected number of deaths over a certain period, using 2016-2019 as baseline period	% change from baseline	Monthly	Eurostat; online data code: demo_mexrt
exc.mortality_2021	Average excess mortality in 2021 as percentage change from expected number of deaths over a certain period, using 2016-2019 as baseline period	% change from baseline	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_mexrt; year 2021
exc.mortality_2022	Average excess mortality in 2022 as percentage change from expected number of deaths over a certain period, using 2016-2019 as baseline period	% change from baseline	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_mexrt; year 2022
exc.mortality_2023	Average excess mortality in 2023 as percentage change from expected number of deaths over a certain period, using 2016-2019 as baseline period	% change from baseline	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: demo_mexrt; year 2023
hosp.disch.cvd_2019	Number of hospital discharges for diseases of the circulatory system (in-patients) in 2019	Number of persons (in-patients) / 100,000	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_co_disch2, year 2019, indicator I

Table 24: Metadata (*continued*)

Variable name	Description	Unit / Format	Coverage	Source
hosp.disch.cvd_2020	Number of hospital discharges for diseases of the circulatory system (in-patients) in 2020	Number of persons (in-patients) / 100,000	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_co_disch2, year 2020, indicator I
hosp.disch.cvd_2021	Number of hospital discharges for diseases of the circulatory system (in-patients) in 2021	Number of persons (in-patients) / 100,000	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: hlth_co_disch2, year 2021, indicator I
pov.se.risk_2019	Share of population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2019	% of general population	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: ilc_peps01n, year 2019, total age & sex, unit PC
pov.se.risk_2020	Share of population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2020	% of general population	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: ilc_peps01n, year 2019, total age & sex, unit PC
pov.se.risk_2021	Share of population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2021	% of general population	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: ilc_peps01n, year 2019, total age & sex, unit PC
pov.se.risk_2022	Share of population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2022	% of general population	Annual	Eurostat; online data code: ilc_peps01n, year 2019, total age & sex, unit PC
HDI_2019	Human Development Index (HDI) for 2019	HDI score	Annual	UNDP
HDI_2020	Human Development Index (HDI) for 2020	HDI score	Annual	UNDP
HDI_2021	Human Development Index (HDI) for 2021	HDI score	Annual	UNDP
retail.recreation_gm	Mobility trends for places like restaurants, cafes, shopping centers, theme parks, museums, libraries, and movie theaters. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
grocery.pharmacy_gm	Mobility trends for places like grocery markets, food warehouses, farmers markets, specialty food shops, drug stores, and pharmacies. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
parks_gm	Mobility trends for places like local parks, national parks, public beaches, marinas, dog parks, plazas, and public gardens. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
transit.stations_gm	Mobility trends for places like public transport hubs such as subway, bus, and train stations. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
workplaces_gm	Mobility trends for places of work. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
residential_gm	Mobility trends for places of residence. In this dataset, the values are computed as national averages.	% change from baseline	Daily	Google Community Mobility Reports
temperature.2m	Air temperature at 2 meters above the surface or land, sea or inland waters.	Degrees Celsius (converted from Kelvin in the original data)	Monthly	Climate Data Store; ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present; Monthly data, with hour reference: 00:00
temperature.dewpoint.2m	Air humidity - the temperature to which the air, at 2 metres above the surface of the Earth, would have to be cooled for saturation to occur	Degrees Celsius (converted from Kelvin in the original data)	Monthly	Climate Data Store; ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present; Monthly data, with hour reference: 00:00
total.precipitation	Total precipitation per hour	mm/h (converted from m/h to mm/h by 1000 multiplication)	Monthly	Climate Data Store; ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present; Monthly data, with hour reference: 00:00
windspeed.10m	Speed of horizontal wind, irrespective of direction, at 10 meters above the surface of Earth	Meters / second	Monthly	Climate Data Store; ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present; Monthly data, with hour reference: 00:00
Supplementary variable for the RDS file: geometry	Spatial coordinates	Multipolygon geometry	-	eurostat R package; function: get_eurostat_geospatial

Due to table size considerations, the table presented here does not contain the **Link** column, which is present in the online version of this file.

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